

Table S12 – AI Resources and the Human Analysis Improvement

Resource	IA and TM Results	Support for human analysis	File
Tree of words	dendrogram with relationships between words from the literature	exploration and familiarisation with the content of the literature. Initial overview	S8_WRDtree.pdf
Tree of the review's titles	dendrogram with relationships between review titles	identification of the areas and terms relevant to the composition of logical expressions	S10_TITREVtree.pdf
Tree of the LogExp	dendrogram with relationships between the logical expressions contained in the literature	structuring the groups based on the relationships between the concepts presented by TM	Figure 3 of the manuscript
LogExp	vector representations and expressions for accessing literature	allow the construction of the LogExp tree	S7_Nlog.xls
HTML-TMs (word and texts)	navigation platform with article and word relationships	HTML-TM was used at all stages to access effective literature	https://aibialab.github.io/HTMLTM_Yoga
Vectors	model for comparability between textual items (words, texts, and LogExp)	context visualization and comparison at all stages	S2_Wwrd.dat; S3_Wtxt.dat; S4_Wlog.dat